

IN SITU SENSING OF RANDOM FAILURE IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

Ali Naghashpour and Suong V. Hoa

Concordia Center for Composites
Department of Mechanical, Industrial and Aerospace Engineering
Concordia University
Center for Research in Polymers and Composites
Montreal, Quebec, Canada
Al_nag@encs.concordia.ca, hoasuon@alcor.concordia.ca

Keywords: ^{Random} failure, Detection, Sensing, In-situ, Carbon nanotubes

ABSTRACT

A new technique to detect random failure in composite structures is presented. The resin matrix material is made conductive by the incorporation of carbon nanotubes (CNTs). Conductive grid points are added on the surface of the large composite panels, so that electrical resistances in the regions between the grid points can be measured. The increase in electrical resistance between grid points is used to determine the increase in deformation (and possibly cracks) at the region between the grid points. It is found that the location of maximum increase in electrical resistance jumps from point to point as the number of cycles during fatigue loading is increased. This shows the random nature of the development of damage in the composites. The technique can detect the occurrence of early failure, usually in the matrix materials. The result of this work brings out the random nature of the early failure in composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

As composites are used more and more in many engineering applications, the need to detect and to predict failure in these structures also becomes more and more important. It is well known that there are many modes of failure in composites. These include matrix cracking, debonding between matrix and fiber, delamination between different layers, and fiber failure. Over the years, a lot of work has been dedicated to the study of failure in composites [1- 5]. Each of these failure mechanisms may occur at different times during the loading process. One type of failure may occur before another type of failure, and one type of failure may be the precursor of another type of failure. In the case of metals, the failure may be divided into two stages: crack initiation and crack propagation. The crack in metals is usually self-similar in which a single crack may become larger and longer as failure progresses but the same crack remains during the whole course of crack initiation and crack propagation. This situation may not apply to composites. This is because there is competition between the different types of failure modes as mentioned above. There is also a significant amount of spatial variation in the properties of the material within a composite structure due to many reasons. Many factors contribute to the variation in the properties of the material within the composite structures. As the load is increased the following sequence of events may be postulated. Firstly, due the variability mentioned above, the deformation within the composites may vary from point to point. Under a nominal applied stress, the deformation may be higher at a certain region as compared to other regions. Secondly, as the load increases, a few matrix cracks may occur at the location of highest deformation. Subsequently, there can be some adjustment of the microstructure of the material (such as fiber rotation and fiber tensioning) as the constraint on the fiber from the matrix is relaxed due to matrix crack or debonding between fibers and matrix. As such, a matrix crack that occurs at location A may weaken or strengthen that location. One scenario of strengthening is illustrated in Fig. 1.

In Fig.1, assume that within a composite structure, there is a fiber with a portion that is mis-oriented (Fig.1a). Upon the loading at the region of fiber misorientation, the matrix cracks since the fiber direction is not along the load direction (Fig.1b). After matrix cracking, the fiber is straightened due to the relaxation of the constraint from the matrix (Fig.1c). After the fiber is straightened, the fiber now can support the load, which makes the region stronger. Due to the fact that the region becomes stronger, as the load level is increased, the matrix crack may not propagate from location A. Instead, there may be another location B away from location A that undergoes larger deformation. This large deformation may create cracking at location B. This jumping process can go from point to point. At a certain value of the load, many of the crack locations may merge together to make a critical crack. This critical crack finally propagates and causes final failure. Usually the time duration from the emergence of the critical crack and the final failure is fairly short. As such, the duration of the crack jumping (may be called the crack initiation period) can be significantly longer than the crack propagation period. In this paper, a new technique has been introduced to detect the crack jumping, and the relationship between the location of the first matrix crack and the final location of failure. The technique utilizes the enhancement of the electrical conductivity of the resin due to the incorporation of carbon nanotubes. The change in the electrical resistances between different grid points in a composite structure is used as indicators for the area under high deformation. In our previous works [6], it was demonstrated that by incorporating CNTs into the epoxy in composite materials, the conductivity of the material was significantly enhanced. By attaching the conductive grid points on the surface of composite plates, it was then possible to detect the occurrence of damages within the composite structure in situ [7-11]. The same methodology is used here for the purpose of detecting the occurrence of random failure in the composite panels. The efficiency of the technique is compared with other structural health monitoring techniques including strain gages and infrared thermography.

Fig.1. Straightening of fiber upon matrix crack, thus strengthening the region A

2. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

2.1. Materials

Multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) with 95% of purity, diameters of 2-20 nm and lengths of 1 μm to more than 10 μm were purchased from Bayer Material Science. Plain weave glass fabrics (15 oz/yd²) purchased from HL. Plasto company, Epon 862 and EPIKURE W purchased from Miller-Stephenson chemical company were utilized as reinforcement, epoxy resin and curing agent respectively.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1 Fabrication of composite panels

Glass fiber/epoxy/MWCNT composite panels were manufactured by hand lay-up method. The epoxy matrix was modified by dispersing 0.30 wt% MWCNTs into epoxy resin mixed with curing agent (26.4 wt%) using three roll milling (EXAKT 80E, EXAKT Technologies Inc.). The modified epoxy matrix was dispersed between four layers of woven glass fabrics. The panels were cured using an autoclave. The nominal thickness of the panels was 1.9 mm.

2.2.2. Specification and electrical arrangement for composite panels

The specification of composite panel is schematically illustrated in Fig. 2. The panels are designed to have relatively large dimensions of 32×14 inch² (see Fig. 2a and b) in order to allow some degree of variability to occur within the large composite structure. It is important to make sure that the stress/strain across the width of the composite panel is uniform. Two sets of small bolts were used on the grips made of rigid steel (see Fig. 2c and d). This is to assure that the difference in deformation from point to point is due mainly to the variability within the material, rather than due to deformation gradient due to the non-uniform loading. Strain gages S1, S2, S3 were installed for this purpose. Also to check for any bending due to the misalignment of the loading, strain gages S2 and S4 were installed on opposite faces of the sample, at the same location within the plane to check for bending. In order to measure the electrical resistance at different locations within the structure, a grid of 24 points (at intervals of 3 inch (76.2 mm)) made from electrically conductive silver-epoxy paste were mounted on the surface of panel.

Fig.2. Composite panels, with electrical grid points and strain gage locations (inches)

2.2.4. Electrical resistance measurement

Two-probe method was used for electrical resistance measurement. A constant source voltage was directly applied and the electrical current was measured to calculate the electrical resistance. The electrodes were connected to the data acquisition system (switch system) and a computer program was written to display the map of electrical resistance results. Electrical resistance was measured using multimeter (Keithley 2100 (61/2)) and switch system (Keithley 7001) linked together. The percent change in electrical resistance (PCER) is calculated by:

$$\Delta R(\%) = \left(\frac{R_F - R_I}{R_I} \right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where R_I refers to the initial electrical resistance while the mean load 67,100 N was maintained on the composite panel at the beginning of the cyclic loading and R_F refers to the resistance after a specified number of cycles ended (the mean load 67100 N was still maintained on the panel).

The mean load of 67,100 N is determined as follows: Ultimate strength of the laminate as determined from coupon test was 360 MPa. This multiplied by the cross section area gives an ultimate load of about 244,000 N. The maximum loading for fatigue is taken to be 50% of the ultimate load or 122,000 N. Using R ratio of 0.1, this gives the minimum load of 12,200 N, a mean load of 67,100 N, and a load amplitude of 54,900 N.

2.2.4. Strain measurement

Strain measurement was performed using conventional metallic strain gauges purchased from Vishay micro measurements Intertechnology. Four strain gauges were attached on the surface of composite panels (see Fig.2). Strains were measured using strain gauge conditioner (2120A), and power supply (2111).

2.2.5. Infrared thermography

Infrared thermography was employed to provide another means for health monitoring during fatigue loading. Infrared radiation emitted from composite panel was captured using an infrared camera in the form of thermal map as a result of the temperature distribution. During the tests, the IR camera (FLIR T450 SC) with 320×240 pixel resolution and temperature sensitivity of 80mK was set on the back side of composite panels. The IR camera was focused on the panels to avoid any heat disturbance from the machine grips.

3. MECHANICAL TESTING

Static and fatigue tests were performed using 250KN MTS hydraulic system.

3.1. Static Tension Testing

Initially, woven glass fabric/epoxy/0.3wt% MWCNT composite coupons were subjected to tensile loading until failure in accordance with ASTM D3039-08 to determine tensile strength of the laminate. Five composite coupons were tested. An average was made for five experiments. The ultimate strength for the laminate was experimentally measured to be 360 ± 20.50 MPa. This value was used to determine the loads for cyclic tension test of large composite panels.

3.2. Tension- Tension Fatigue Testing

Ten 32×14 inch² clean composite panels were subjected to tension-tension cyclic fatigue testing while the electrical resistances, strain and temperature distributions were measured. Tension/tension cyclic load was applied to composite panels with mean load of 67,100 N, equivalent to 50% of the maximum tensile load, and an amplitude of 54,900 N. In these tests, large composite panels were cycled between minimum and maximum loads at a frequency of 5Hz at different peak loads. The tests were periodically paused after every 100 cycles. This specific loading cycle was chosen for fatigue testing to simulate the effect of relatively high stress cycles beyond typical service loads. The load, strain, thermal and electrical signals in real-time were simultaneously recorded.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Checking for uniformity of strain distribution across the panel width

To ensure that the loading is uniformly applied across the width of the composite panels, strains were measured at maximum load of different loading cycles using four strain gauges as shown in Fig.2. Fig.3 shows the distribution of strain measured at maximum load at 50, 100, 150, 200, 250, 300, 350 and 400 cycles (for panel 1). The results show that the strain distribution is uniform.

Fig.3. Strain results measured using four strain gauges mounted at different locations.

4.2. Checking for uniformity in the distribution of electrical resistances

The uniformity of the electrical resistances across grid points in the composite structure depends on the amount of carbon nanotubes used, and the degree of mixing [6, 7]. It is important to assure that there is a certain degree of uniformity of electrical resistance between the grid points before the mechanical loading. This is to eliminate any effect of non-uniform loading on the occurrence of random failure.

4.3. Variation in Percent change in electrical resistance (PCER) as function of number of fatigue cycles.

A total of 10 large composite panels were made for experimentation. Due to the lack of space, only the typical results from plate 1 are presented here. More details on the results can be found in reference [12].

Fig. 4a shows the evolution of the locations of maximum PCER. Initially, location C (between probe points 13 and 14) has the maximum PCER. As the number of cycles is increased, the maximum PCER position changes to location B. Location A initially had lower value of PCER, but the PCER at this location accelerates and overtakes the other locations, to be the final location for failure. Fig. 4b shows the photograph of composite panel 1 after final failure. Other panels show similar patterns.

5. COMPARISON WITH INFRARED THERMOGRAPHY

Fig. 4c, d, e and f show thermographs taken by infrared camera at different number of cycles for composite panel 1. From these figures, it appears that infrared thermography technique is able to

detect the location of final failure, as early as at 100 cycles of loading, since there are red spots at the center of the laminate at this stage. However the red spots are the location of the strain gages. As the material is deformed, the strain gages heat up and they are detected. The thermographs do not show red spots at locations C and B. As such, the thermography technique cannot detect the location for the occurrence of failure in the early stage. It can only pick up the occurrence of damage at about 10,000 cycles, which is very close to final failure at 11,712 cycles.

6. DISCUSSION FOR THE ABILITY OF THE TECHNIQUE

It can be seen from the results that the technique using grid points on electrically conductive composites (using CNTs) can detect the evolution of the development of damage within the composite structure. This is more sensitive as compared to the techniques using thermography, or strain gages. In fact, as compared to other techniques for evaluation of the integrity of composite structures, such as fiber optics, acoustic emission etc. this technique of using grid point on electrically conductive composites (using CNTs) is a lot more sensitive. The technique is also easy to use. Besides, the ability to detect the damage, it can also locate and quantify the damage [11]. The technique of using grid points on electrically conductive composites can detect the jumping of locations of damage in the composite structure. Other techniques such as strain gage, or thermography cannot detect that. Early cracks (matrix cracks) do jump around from location to location as the load is increased. Even though great efforts were taken to keep the manufacturing parameters to be consistent, variability in composite structures occurs. Certainly the quality and consistency of the laminates may vary depending on the experience of the operator, and the availability of equipment. However, this variability does not affect the significance and validity of the proposed technique. In fact, the proposed technique is independent of the quality or variability of the laminates. The technique is sensitive enough to pick up these variabilities, and it can be used as a way to check for quality of the laminates.

7. CONCLUSION

A new technique for in-situ detection of the random occurrence of areas of large deformation (and possible cracks) has been presented. This technique utilizes the enhanced electrical conductivity of the matrix resin to monitor the evolution of the electrical resistances between grid points in the composites structure. The results showed that the regions of high deformation (and possible cracks) jump from point to point as the number of cycles increase. The technique is more sensitive to detect the occurrence of damage as compared to many other techniques such as strain gage or thermography used.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Financial support from the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada is appreciated.

Fig.4: **Composite panel 1:** (a) PCER as a function of the number of cycles for the locations of high PCER, (b) photograph of broken composite panel 1, Thermal maps of composite panel 1 at different cycles: (c) 100, (d) 1000, (e) 10000 and (f) immediately after fracture (11,712)

REFERENCES

- [1] Puck A. and Schneider W., "On the failure mechanisms and failure criteria of filament wound glass fibre/resin composites", *Plastics and Polymers, The Plastics Institute Transactions and Journal*, February 1969, pp. 33-42, Pergamon Press, UK.
- [2] Tsai S.W., and Wu E.M., "A general theory of strength for anisotropic materials", *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1971, Vol. 5, pp. 58-80.
- [3] Hashin, Z., and Rotem, A., "A Fatigue Failure Criterion for Fiber-Reinforced Materials," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 7, 1973, pp. 448-464.
- [3] M.J. Hinton, A.S. Kaddour, and P.D. Soden, eds, "Failure criteria in fibre-reinforced polymer composites- The World Wide Failure exercise", Elsevier, 2004.
- [4] M. May and S.R. Hallet, "An advanced model for initiation and propagation of damage under fatigue loading, part I: Model formulation", *J. Composite Structures*, 93, 2011, pp. 2340-2349.
- [5] Hossein Ghayoor, Suong Van Hoa , and Catherine Marsden, " A micro mechanical study of stress concentrations in composites", *Composites, Part B*, 132, 2018, pp. 115-124.
- [6] Rosca, I.D. and Hoa, S.V., "Highly conductive multiwall carbon nanotube and epoxy composites produced by three-roll milling", *Carbon*, Vol. 47, 2009, 1958-1968.
- [7] Nofar R., Hoa S.V., and Pugh M., "Failure detection and monitoring in polymer matrix composites subjected to static and dynamic loads using carbon nanotube networks", *Composites Science and Technology*, 69, 2009, pp. 1599-1606.
- [8] Hesna-Zamal, H. and Hoa, S.V., "Fatigue damage behavior of glass/epoxy composites using carbon nanotubes as sensors", *Proc. 26th symposium of the international committee on aeronautical fatigue*, Montreal, June 1-3, 2011.
- [9] Naghashpour A., and Hoa S.V., "In situ monitoring of through-thickness strain in glass fiber/epoxy composite laminates using carbon nanotube sensors", *Composites Science and Technology*, 78, 2013, pp. 41-47.
- [10] Naghashpour A., and Hoa S.V., "Technique for real-time detection, location and quantification of damages in large polymer composite structures made of electrically non-conductive fibers and carbon nanotube networks", *Nanotechnology*, 24, 45, Nov. 2013.
- [11] Naghashpour A. and Hoa S.V., "A technique for real-time monitoring, locating and quantifying damage in large polymer composite structures made of carbon fibers and carbon nanotube networks", *Structural Health Monitoring*, DOI 10.1177/1475921714546063, 2014.
- [12]. Naghashpour A., and Hoa S.V., "A technique for in-situ detection of random failure in composite structures under cyclic loading", *J. of Composite Materials*, 2019, DOI: 10.1177/002199839131.